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Abstract

The Communication and Dissemination Plan provides an overview of the communication and dissemination strategy of ASSESS DHT. It covers an overview of the communication and dissemination goals and objectives, target audience(s) and messaging, communication and dissemination channels, tools, and structures. Further, it lays out the projects' approach towards the monitoring, reporting and evaluation of the success of the communication and dissemination efforts undertaken by ASSESS DHT.

Statement of originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of HaDEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....5

1 Introduction.....6

 1.1 Scope and objectives of the deliverable6

2 Communication and dissemination strategy7

 2.1 Goals and objectives.....7

 2.2 Target audience(s) and messaging7

 2.2.1 Stakeholder identification and classification7

 2.2.2 Stakeholder messages.....9

3 Communication and dissemination channels15

 3.1 Direct exchanges15

 3.2 Websites.....15

 3.3 Social Media.....17

 3.3.1 X.....19

 3.3.2 LinkedIn19

 3.4 Events.....20

 3.5 Dissemination materials.....20

 3.6 (Scientific) publications21

4 Communication and dissemination tools and structures23

 4.1 Virtual Communication Office Team23

 4.2 Communication and dissemination reporting and planning tool23

 4.3 Canva.....24

 4.4 Webinar tools25

 4.5 Collaboration platforms and tools for enabling interaction with stakeholders25

5 Monitoring and reporting indicators and evaluation26

FIGURES

Figure 1. Initial stakeholder mapping under the five-group classification 8

Figure 2. Screenshot ASSESS DHT website landing page.....16

Figure 3. Campaign LinkedIn post on social media.....17

Figure 4. X example post19

Figure 5. LinkedIn example post19

Figure 6. ASSESS DHT two-pager21

Figure 7. Examples of visual campaigns created using Canva.....24

Figure 8. ASSESS DHT brand kit on Canva24

TABLES

Table 1. Stakeholder identification and classification7

Table 2. Stakeholder groups and their relevance to ASSESS DHT.....8

Table 3. Origin of the initiative9

Table 4. Key project results and milestones10

Table 5. Stakeholder-specific messages11

Table 6. Overview of consortium members’ websites16

Table 7. Social media follower numbers17

Table 8. Milestones social media campaigns18

Table 9. Impact indicators for ASSESS DHT communication targets26

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This Deliverable, D1.5 Communication and Dissemination Plan, provides an overview of the communication and dissemination strategy of ASSESS DHT. In doing so, it provides an overview of the communication and dissemination goals and objectives, target audience(s) and messaging in chapter 2. The subchapter 2.1 provides an overview of the four dissemination objectives that will help the project achieve its overall ASSESS DHT dissemination goal; namely, to secure Health Technology Assessment (HTA) Agency endorsement and to foster the developer's understanding of the assessment framework put forward by the project. In subchapter 2.2, both the identification and classification of stakeholder groups that ASSESS DHT aims to address are outlined. The relevance of each stakeholder group to the project is detailed, illustrating how this understanding shapes targeted communication efforts. Additionally, stakeholder messages are categorised into thematic areas to highlight the project's origin, key results, and milestones. Finally, tailored messaging approaches and corresponding examples are provided for every relevant stakeholder.

This deliverable further provides an overview of the communication and dissemination channels, tools, and structures that it has established thus far and will utilise in the future in chapters 3 and 4.

The communication and dissemination channels that are discussed include:

- Direct exchanges
- Project website and consortium partner websites
- Social media (Twitter/X and LinkedIn)
- Events (webinars, workshops, conferences)
- Dissemination materials
- Scientific (open access) publications

Chapter 3 pays particular attention to the timing of using these communication and dissemination channels, as well as their utilisation for communicating the project milestones. The communication and dissemination tools and structures that are discussed in chapter 4 of this deliverable are:

- The virtual communication office team
- Communication and dissemination reporting and planning tool
- Canva
- Webinar tools
- Collaboration platform and tools for enabling interaction with stakeholders.

Further, chapter 5 of this deliverable lays out the projects' approach towards the monitoring, reporting and evaluation of the success of the communication and dissemination efforts undertaken by ASSESS DHT.

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope and objectives of the deliverable

This deliverable lays out the overarching communication and dissemination objectives and strategy, including specific target audiences for ASSESS DHT. Further, the deliverable details the channels, tools and structures the project employs to achieve its communication and dissemination objectives, as well as the approach towards the monitoring and evaluation of reporting indicators. In doing so, it defines an action plan driven by work package (WP) 1 lead EMPIRICA and put into action by all consortium partners. This plan will be executed in T1.6 External communication, content production, events and media campaigns to maximise impact throughout the entire duration of the project (M1-M36).

This document is structured as follows:

- Chapter 2 provides an overview of the communication and dissemination strategy and focuses on target audiences and associated messaging.
- Chapter 3 provides an overview of the communication and dissemination channels that are or will be utilised by ASSESS DHT.
- Chapter 4 provides an overview of the communication and dissemination tools and structures employed by the ASSESS DHT consortium.
- Chapter 5 provides an overview of ASSESS DHT's approach towards monitoring and evaluation and presents indicators that will be used to measure the success of the implementation of the communication and dissemination plan.

2 Communication and dissemination strategy

This chapter of the deliverable lays out the communication and dissemination strategy, consisting of the goals and objectives as well as an overview of the target audience(s) and associated messaging.

2.1 Goals and objectives

Overall, the ASSESS DHT dissemination activities aim to secure HTA agency endorsement and to foster the developer's understanding of the assessment framework put forward by the project. The following four dissemination objectives were defined to contribute to this overarching dissemination goal.

Dissemination Objectives (DO)

- **DO1. Raise awareness:** Engage with stakeholders and raise awareness about the necessity of harmonising different DHT approaches to assessment and the benefits of mutual assessments recognised across settings and countries. Advocate for adoption of such approaches and encourage key players, especially HTA bodies, to join the work and use the framework and tools produced in the project.
- **DO2. Engagement of key stakeholders:** Continuously engage and create opportunities for receiving input, delivering information and ensuring adoption among relevant stakeholders.
- **DO3. Scientific publications, posters and participation in conferences:** Promote the scientific work, especially from WPs 2 and 3, to a wider audience and ensure it is well understood and accepted.
- **DO4. Post-project action planning to facilitate future uptake of ASSESS DHT results:** Think about next steps beyond the project and address points of sustainability, incl. how the tools are to be used (e.g. licensing), what training can be offered in the future, what capacities are required, etc.

2.2 Target audience(s) and messaging

2.2.1 Stakeholder identification and classification

The ASSESS DHT consortium identified five primary target audience groups for its communication and dissemination objectives, based on each group's role in digital health technologies:

Table 1. Stakeholder identification and classification

Groups	Stakeholders
Users	Healthcare providers Patients Caregivers
Developers	Industry Healthcare authorities who procure development services for DHTs Technology developers
Researchers	Academic and research institutions Ethics committees and institutional review boards Professional associations and societies
Governing bodies	National and regional health authorities Health Technology Assessment (HTA) bodies European data protection authorities

	Standards Development Organisations HTA HAG (Heads of Agencies Group) Centres of excellence International organisations that oversee assessment and utilisation of DHTs
Financiers	Ministries of health National health insurance programs Health insurance companies Government agencies

An initial mapping of relevant stakeholders under this five-group classification was created to serve as the foundational basis for the project's communication and dissemination activities. This mapping can be seen in the following figure.

Figure 1. Initial stakeholder mapping under the five-group classification

Recognising the relevance of each stakeholder group informs ASSESS DHT's communication strategy as it helps target messages efficiently. Consequently, the following table presents each stakeholder group's relevance to ASSESS DHT.

Table 2. Stakeholder groups and their relevance to ASSESS DHT

Group	Relevance to the ASSESS DHT consortium
Users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Primary beneficiaries of improved DHTs. • Provide real-world feedback on DHT usability and the clinical outcomes associated with its use.
Developers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drive innovation in DHTs, creating solutions that meet market demands. • Ensure products align with healthcare standards through collaboration with researchers and governing bodies.
Researchers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conduct research on DHT efficacy and provide evidence-based support for

	<p>adoption.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovate through academic collaboration, ensuring scientific rigor and validation.
Governing bodies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shape HTA, interoperability, and funding frameworks, supporting the adoption and integration of DHTs within healthcare system IT infrastructures. • Address ethical, legal, data protection, cybersecurity, and compliance considerations, promoting a cohesive environment for DHT adoption. • Robust and transparent frameworks to send clear signals to innovators about how value in the field of DHT is assessed.
Financiers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evidence-based funding and reimbursement decisions for DHTs, facilitating patient access to innovative solutions. • Assess cost-effectiveness and benefits, supporting sustainable funding models. • Clear and robust processes to help innovators generate the necessary evidence to inform and navigate pricing and reimbursement processes.

2.2.2 Stakeholder messages

Stakeholder messages have been organised into key thematic areas to emphasise the project's foundational elements and progression:

- **Messages pertaining to ASSESS DHT's origin:** aimed at underpinning its credibility, reliability, and trustworthiness.
- **Messages on key project results and milestones:** These messages communicate both short-term project progress and potential long-term implications. The messages tailored to communicate the milestones will be further discussed with regard to specific social media campaigns in *Table 8. Milestones social media campaigns*.
- **Stakeholder-specific messages** that can be efficiently delivered by project partners based on the target group, for example, during conferences and events.

Messages for each of these thematic areas are reflected in separate tables below. It is essential to highlight that the messages listed in the tables below are concise to ensure adaptability across multiple communication platforms (e.g., social media, direct exchanges, etc.). However, brevity should not compromise critical context; thus, project partners are encouraged to share multiple messages where appropriate, always providing a reference back to the project website for comprehensive information (e.g., as demonstrated in the initial message under "origin of the initiative").

This part of the document is intended to be dynamic, with stakeholder messages being continuously refined and updated based on feedback from stakeholders and insights gained from consortium partners' interactions. The messaging and its effectiveness will be reflected upon in upcoming deliverables pertaining to the communication and dissemination efforts of ASSESS DHT (D1.6, D1.7).

Table 3. Origin of the initiative

<p>Communication Objective: Underpin the credibility, reliability and trustworthiness of the initiative</p>
<p>Under the European Commission's mandate, ASSESS DHT is working to harmonise the assessment of Digital Health Technologies across Europe.</p> <p>ASSESS DHT is a key European effort to boost the use of reliable Digital Health Technologies.</p> <p>ASSESS DHT is a European initiative that will increase the adoption of trustworthy and effective Digital Health Technologies across Europe, enabling a more coherent digital single market, for health systems and patients to access DHT from all over Europe and giving industry a European market.</p>

The overarching objective of ASSESS DHT is to consolidate and streamline existing methods and tools for approval of innovative DHT and develop a new fit-for-purpose generic (overarching) assessment framework, harmonised for Europe and aligned with the [European Health Data Space \(EHDS\)](#) Regulation proposal.

ASSESS DHT's new assessment framework will also be presented in a way that it can seamlessly be adapted to different contexts of work and aims, catering to the potential variability between settings to address the methodological challenges in assessing DHTs. It aims to evaluate their added value and health benefits for patients and support the digital transformation of health systems.

As pointed out above, ASSESS DHT's communication regarding the project progress will highlight in particular the nine project milestones that were defined before the beginning of the project. The associated messages are displayed in *Table 4. Key project results and milestones*.

Table 4. Key project results and milestones

Communication Objective: Highlight key project results and milestones¹

Milestone 1: All project enabling resources are operational

- Communication's goal: Inform stakeholders that ASSESS DHT has successfully established all necessary resources to support the project, i.e. the project's website, quality plan and handbook.
- Example:
We are excited to announce that all enabling resources for the ASSESS DHT project are now fully operational. This milestone ensures our capacity to deliver reliable and effective assessments of Digital Health Technologies.

Milestone 2: Call for tender for a case study on assessment of an AI-based technology used in radiology

- Communication's goal: Invite stakeholders to participate in a call to evaluate an AI-based radiology technology in a significant case study for utilising the framework for assessing digital health technologies established by ASSESS DHT.
- Example:
ASSESS DHT has issued a call for tender for a groundbreaking case study on AI-based technology in radiology. We invite experts to participate in this critical evaluation.

Milestone 3: Taxonomy developed and presented to external experts for feedback

- Communication's goal: Provide information regarding the development of a comprehensive taxonomy of digital health technologies for assessment purposes and request feedback from external experts for refining and validating the framework.
- Example:
ASSESS DHT has developed a comprehensive taxonomy for Digital Health Technologies and presented it to external experts for feedback. Your insights are invaluable to us!

Milestone 4: Initial version of manual piloting assessment methods for digital health technologies

- Communication's goal: Inform stakeholders about the launch of the preliminary manual for piloting assessment methods, emphasising its significance in standardising DHT evaluations. This manual relates to the consolidated ASSESS DHT framework with all final criteria.
- Example:
The initial version of our manual for piloting assessment methods for Digital Health Technologies is

¹ The information in this table is intended to shape the overall communication approach plan. It outlines the key project results and milestones and provides a premise for targeted messaging. However, as previously remarked, section four will discuss in detail the specific messages tailored to communicate these milestones.

now available. This is a crucial step in standardising DHT evaluations.

Milestone 5: Initial versions of all data related criteria ready for inclusion in our framework

- Communication's goal: Announcing the development of initial data-related criteria for the assessment framework, underscoring its role in providing thorough evaluations. The data related criteria relate to issues such as data protection, ethical AI, regulatory compliance, data quality, interoperability, FAIR data, security measures.
- Example:
We have finalised the initial versions of all data-related criteria for our assessment framework. This milestone is essential for conducting comprehensive DHT evaluations.

Milestone 6: Initial version of the Life-cycle assessment of DHT

- Communication's goal: Communicate the release of the initial version of the life-cycle assessment for DHTs while underscoring its role in evaluating technologies' long-term impact. This relates to the specific needs associated with iterative evaluations.
- Example:
The initial version of our life-cycle assessment for Digital Health Technologies is complete. This will help us assess the quality of the evidence at the different stages of the life-cycle of DHTs.

Milestone 7: European tool to optimise approach to addressing gaps in evidence development plans

- Communication's goal: Introduce stakeholders to the European tool designed to optimise evidence development plans, which is an essential element in improving DHT assessments. The tool is intended for developers to reflect their draft evidence, discuss gaps and improve it pre-submission.
- Example:
Introducing our new European tool for optimising evidence development plans. This tool is essential to address potential gaps in the evidence base collected early on throughout the development of a DHT.

Milestone 8: Launch Open call for evidence submissions to gather feedback on usability of outputs

- Communication's goal: Invite stakeholders to participate in a call for evidence submissions, encouraging them to provide feedback on the usability of the ASSESS DHT's results and outputs.
- Example:
We are launching an open call for evidence submissions to gather feedback on the usability of our results. Your input is crucial to refining our assessments.

Milestone 9: ASSESS DHT Repository is online

- Communication's goal: Inform stakeholders about the launch of the ASSESS DHT Repository and the valuable information it provides. In particular, external stakeholders should be made aware of their access to the initial evidence merging from the ASSESS DHT case studies and the framework the project has developed.
- Example:
The DHT Repository is now online, offering a wealth of information on validated Digital Health Technologies. This is a valuable resource that can fuel your innovation and keep you at the forefront of the industry's latest developments.

Table 5. Stakeholder-specific messages

Communication Objective: Provide messages for each stakeholder group

USERS

Healthcare Providers

- Communication's goal: Inform healthcare providers about how ASSESS DHT validates the reliability and efficacy of DHTs, ensuring these technologies meet clinical needs and enhance patient care.
- Example:
Healthcare providers: Elevate your practice with ASSESS DHT's validated Digital Health Technologies.

Our assessments ensure you integrate reliable and effective tools, improving patient outcomes and streamlining care processes.

Patients

- Communication's goal: Communicate to patients how ASSESS DHT ensures the safety and effectiveness of DHTs, improving their health outcomes and user experience.
- Example:
Patients: Discover the benefits of ASSESS DHT's rigorously tested Digital Health Technologies. Our validated solutions are designed to enhance your health management and provide better care experiences.

Caregivers

- Communication's goal: Highlight to caregivers how ASSESS DHT supports the adoption of reliable DHTs that aid in patient management and care efficiency.
- Example:
Caregivers: Empower your caregiving with ASSESS DHT's validated Digital Health Technologies. Our tools support patient well-being and streamline your daily routines, making caregiving more efficient.

DEVELOPERS

Industry

- Communication's goal: Convey to industry stakeholders how ASSESS DHT provides a harmonised assessment framework, facilitating market entry and regulatory compliance for new DHTs.
- Example
Industry leaders: Accelerate your DHT market entry with ASSESS DHT's harmonised assessment framework, including our fast-track pipeline. Ensure compliance and acceptance across Europe with our comprehensive assessment tools.

Healthcare Authorities who Procure Development Services for DHTs

- Communication's goal: Explain to healthcare authorities how ASSESS DHT ensures that procured DHTs meet high standards of quality and effectiveness, supporting their integration into healthcare systems.
- Example:
Healthcare authorities: Trust ASSESS DHT's assessments to procure high-quality Digital Health Technologies. Enhance healthcare delivery and patient outcomes with our validated solutions.

Technology Developers

- Communication's goal: Inform technology developers about how ASSESS DHT's guidelines and assessment processes streamline the development of compliant and market-ready DHTs.
- Example:
Technology developers: Streamline your DHT development with ASSESS DHT's guidelines and assessment processes. Bring innovative solutions to market efficiently, meeting stringent quality standards.

RESEARCHERS

Academic and Research Institutions

- Communication's goal: Communicate to academic and research institutions how ASSESS DHT supports evidence-based research and validation of DHTs, fostering innovation and scientific advancement.
- Example:
Researchers: Advance DHT research with ASSESS DHT's comprehensive validation methods. Collaborate with us to ensure your innovations meet the highest standards and foster scientific advancement.

Ethics Committees and Institutional Review Boards

- Communication's goal: Highlight to ethics committees and IRBs how ASSESS DHT ensures that DHTs

adhere to ethical standards, promoting safe and responsible technological development.

- Example:
Ethics committees: Guarantee that DHTs are developed responsibly and safely with ASSESS DHT's ethical assessments. Uphold ethical standards in all technology assessments.

Professional Associations and Societies

- Communication's goal: Explain to professional associations and societies how ASSESS DHT integrates validated DHTs into clinical practice guidelines, including the adoption of tele-health services, enhancing professional standards and patient care.
- Example:
Professional associations: Integrate ASSESS DHT's validated Digital Health Technologies into your clinical practice guidelines. Ensure your members have access to the latest and most reliable technologies.

GOVERNING BODIES

National and Regional Health Authorities

- Communication's goal: Inform health authorities about how ASSESS DHT's harmonised assessment framework supports regulatory compliance and facilitates the integration of DHTs into national and regional healthcare systems.
- Example:
Health authorities: Implement ASSESS DHT's harmonised framework to streamline the adoption of innovative Digital Health Technologies. Improve healthcare delivery across regions with our validated solutions.

Health Technology Assessment (HTA) Bodies

- Communication's goal: Explain to HTA bodies how ASSESS DHT collaborates on developing comprehensive evaluation criteria that ensure the value and impact of DHTs are thoroughly assessed.
- Example:
HTA bodies: Enhance your technology evaluation processes with ASSESS DHT's comprehensive assessment tools. Ensure thorough and accurate assessments of Digital Health Technologies.

European Data Protection Authorities

- Communication's goal: Communicate to data protection authorities how ASSESS DHT ensures DHTs comply with data protection regulations, safeguarding patient privacy and data security.
- Example:
Data protection authorities: Ensure compliance with data protection regulations using ASSESS DHT's validated Digital Health Technologies. Safeguard patient privacy and data security with our assessments.

Standards Development Organisations

- Communication's goal: Highlight to standards organisations how ASSESS DHT works to establish and promote rigorous standards for DHTs, enhancing their quality and reliability.
- Example:
Standards organisations: Collaborate with ASSESS DHT to establish rigorous standards for Digital Health Technologies. Enhance quality and reliability with our validated assessment framework.

HTA HAG (Heads of Agencies Group)

- Communication's goal: Inform the HTA HAG about how ASSESS DHT supports European cooperation on HTA for Digital Health Technologies, particularly in developing Joint Clinical Assessments and fostering a cohesive HTA environment.
- Example:
HTA HAG: Discover how ASSESS DHT bolsters European cooperation on HTA for Digital Health Technologies, aiding in the development of Joint Clinical Assessments and promoting a cohesive HTA environment.

Centres of Excellence

- Communication's goal: Communicate to centres of excellence how ASSESS DHT supports the research and implementation of cutting-edge DHTs, fostering innovation and best practices.
- Example:
Centres of excellence: Collaborate with ASSESS DHT to advance the research and implementation of cutting-edge Digital Health Technologies. Foster innovation and best practices in healthcare.

International Organisations that Oversee Assessment and Utilisation of DHTs

- Communication's goal: Inform international organisations how ASSESS DHT promotes global standards and cooperation in the assessment and utilisation of DHTs, ensuring their effective adoption worldwide.
- Example:
International organisations: Support global standards and cooperation in the assessment and utilisation of Digital Health Technologies with ASSESS DHT. Ensure effective adoption worldwide.

FINANCIERS

Ministries of Health

- Communication's goal: Explain to ministries of health how ASSESS DHT provides evidence-based assessments of DHTs, supporting informed funding decisions that improve public health outcomes.
- Example:
Ministries of Health: Make informed funding decisions with ASSESS DHT's evidence-based assessments of Digital Health Technologies. Improve public health outcomes and drive digital transformation with our validated solutions.

National Health Insurance Programs

- Communication's goal: Communicate to national health insurance programs how ASSESS DHT validates the cost-effectiveness of DHTs, ensuring reimbursed solutions provide significant health benefits.
- Example:
National health insurance: Ensure cost-effective and beneficial DHTs with ASSESS DHT's comprehensive evaluations. Support patient access to innovative health solutions.

Health Insurance Companies

- Communication's goal: Highlight to health insurance companies how ASSESS DHT's reliable assessments facilitate the inclusion of effective DHTs in their coverage plans.
- Example:
Insurance companies: Assess the cost-effectiveness and benefits of Digital Health Technologies with ASSESS DHT's rigorous evaluations. Ensure sustainable funding models for innovative solutions.

Government Agencies

- Communication's goal: Inform government agencies how ASSESS DHT assists in the evaluation and approval of DHTs, ensuring funded initiatives are effective and aligned with national health priorities.
- Example:
Government agencies: Support the adoption of innovative DHTs with ASSESS DHT's harmonised assessment framework. Ensure regulatory compliance and effective integration into healthcare systems.

3 Communication and dissemination channels

This chapter presents an overview of the communication and dissemination channels utilised by ASSESS DHT. The strategy will be put into action in T1.6 following a multi-channel strategy. The following channels will be utilised and are elaborated upon below:

- Direct exchanges
- Project website and consortium partner websites
- Social media (Twitter/X and LinkedIn)
- Events (webinars, workshops, conferences)
- Dissemination materials
- Scientific (open access) publications

Regarding the timing of the utilisation of the communication and dissemination channels, ASSESS DHT will follow a two-fold strategy. Firstly, for communication and dissemination campaigns associated with the milestones are pre-determined and will follow the timing of the milestones themselves. This is further elaborated upon in *Table 8. Milestones social media campaigns*. Additional social media campaigns will be flexibly scheduled in accordance with the progress of the project. To ensure optimal scheduling, campaigns will be discussed with the Virtual Communication Office Team (see p. 23) and then fed into overall social media planning.

This approach regarding timing will allow for a fixed content plan regarding the milestones, while maintaining the flexibility to timely communicate project results and engage with stakeholders as needed by the project.

3.1 Direct exchanges

Direct exchanges with individuals, projects and organisations of different kinds are an excellent opportunity to spread ASSESS DHT's work and raise people's interest in the project. Moreover, they provide a platform where both parties can mutually benefit by gauging synergies and identifying opportunities for collaboration. Whenever possible, direct exchanges are the preferred mode of communication of ASSESS DHT as it is very efficient and impactful. ASSESS DHT has already initiated several direct exchanges, for example with its sister project EDIHTA.

The consortium will continue to exchange information directly with relevant stakeholders to increase its reach and enable direct collaboration. ASSESS DHT will further advance its strategy to identify relevant collaborations. This will be done in particular between the tasks T1.6 and T6.1, but also involving all partners.

3.2 Websites

ASSESS DHT established its website at the beginning of the project to provide a "one-stop shop" of information on the project for interested stakeholders. The project website was launched on 29 February 2024 and can be accessed at: <https://assess-dht.eu/>.

The website reports on the ASSESS DHT progress and results and acts as an information platform for stakeholders to learn more about the project, its vision and results. Using a webpage allows us to provide a centralised and accessible resource for all relevant information, ensuring transparency and engagement with our target audience.

Figure 2. Screenshot ASSESS DHT website landing page

The 'About' provides the project description, information about the consortium (including partner summaries, their roles in the project, websites, and social media links), and a third section dedicated to the pool of experts of the project. The 'News and Events' section is dedicated to informing the audience about the latest events involving the project. The sections 'Contact Us' and 'Get Involved' aim to clarify doubts and invite stakeholders and interested parties to connect with the project. The ASSESS DHT website is described in more detail in D1.1, "Project website and dissemination channels".

Going forward, the website is envisaged to be continuously updated as the project progresses. In addition to the existing headers "about", "news", "events" and "contact us", the website will also present the project outputs under a new header, namely "results" which will be implemented to showcase key outcomes and accepted public deliverables.

In addition to the ASSESS DHT project website, project partners may additionally publish news items regarding ASSESS DHT on their own website to disseminate information on the project further. The consortium members' websites are listed below.

Table 6. Overview of consortium members' websites

Consortium member	Website URL
AIHTA	https://aihta.at/page/homepage/de
BECA	https://bettercare.es/
EMPIRICA	https://empirica.com/
FPS	https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/
i-HD	https://www.i-hd.eu/
IDF	https://idf.org/europe/
NICE	https://www.nice.org.uk/
T4C	https://www.tech4care.it/
TLV	https://www.tlv.se/in-english/
TUB	https://www.tu.berlin/
TUD	https://tu-dresden.de/
ULB	https://www.ulb.be/
UOXF	https://www.ox.ac.uk/

3.3 Social Media

In addition to the project website and direct exchanges, ASSESS DHT utilises LinkedIn and X (formerly Twitter) as a means of project dissemination and engagement activities. In doing so, it combines ad hoc and long-term social media campaigns, as well as engagement in the overall HTA discourse via the re-posting and commenting functions on the respective platforms. This also allows for the creation of synergies with other projects in the realm of HTA, such as the sister project EDIHTA, as interactions increase the visibility of posts and associated messages.

The consortium's involvement is through the vCOT meetings, where they are informed about social media campaigns, strategies, and posts planned. During these meetings (which occur once per month), all partners have the opportunity to share events they will be attending related to the project. This makes it possible to promote such events on social media. These campaigns have the potential to spread the project's ideas and indirectly invite more specialists to get involved.

Table 7. Social media follower numbers

Platform	Account Name	URL	Followers as of July 1st, 2024
X (formerly Twitter)	@AssessDht	https://twitter.com/AssessDht	55
LinkedIn	ASSESS DHT	https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/assess-dht	261

The first campaign involving the participation of partners is "Get to know the ASSESS DHT consortium." Each week, social media posts invite our audience to learn more about the project, its partners, and their roles. The campaign also introduces the people behind the action. On LinkedIn, our most popular platform, since the campaign was released and people were tagged, there has been a noticeable increase in the number of followers and interactions. The campaign started on 09 May 2024, and the last post will be posted on 25 July 2024.

Figure 3. Campaign LinkedIn post on social media

ASSESS DHT will further accompany each of its milestones with a dedicated communication campaign. Chapter 2 provides an overview of example messages, whereas the table below presents an overview of the current considerations regarding specific social media campaigns.

Table 8. Milestones social media campaigns

Nr	Milestone title	Social media campaign	Timing (Month)
1	All project enabling resources are operational	Announcement post on X and LinkedIn, including visuals.	6
2	Call for tender for a case study on assessment of an AI-based technology used in radiology	Call to action post on X and LinkedIn to announce the call for tender, including visuals. Potential video message to announce the call for tender. Potential to host a Q&A session to answer applicant's questions.	6 ²
3	Taxonomy developed and presented to external experts for feedback	Announcement post on X and LinkedIn, including an infographic on the taxonomy. Potential promotion of opportunities to provide feedback via X and LinkedIn.	10
4	Initial version of manual piloting assessment methods for digital health technologies	Announcement post on X and LinkedIn, including visuals.	15
5	Initial versions of all data related criteria ready for inclusion in our framework	Announcement post on X and LinkedIn, including visuals.	12
6	Initial version of life-cycle assessment of DHT	Announcement post on X and LinkedIn, including visuals. Potential short explanation video on the importance of life-cycle assessment of DHTs, to be disseminated via X and LinkedIn.	18
7	European tool to optimise approach to addressing gaps in evidence development plans	Announcement post on X and LinkedIn, including infographic on the tool's functionalities.	18
8	Launch Open call for evidence submissions to gather feedback on usability of outputs	Call to action post on X and LinkedIn to announce the open call for evidence submissions, including visuals. Potential to host a Q&A session to answer applicant's questions.	20
9	ASSESS DHT Repository is online	Announcement post on X and LinkedIn, including an infographic on the repository's functionalities. Potential video on the functionalities of the repository to be shared via X and LinkedIn.	24

² It is foreseen that the date for Milestone 2 will be amended. However, as the changes are not finalised, the current official timeline is reflected.

3.3.1 X

The first post on X (formerly Twitter) was made on 12 March 2024 to promote the recently launched website. We chose to use X due to its effectiveness in reaching a comprehensive and diverse audience, particularly within the digital health community, where our partners and their collaborators predominantly utilise it. X provides an ideal platform for ASSESS DHT to engage in discussions, stay tuned to relevant topics, live-post events, summarise content shared on LinkedIn, and share partners' perspectives on relevant themes and their participation in events.

Figure 4. X example post

3.3.2 LinkedIn

The project page was launched on 29 February 2024, with the first post highlighting the website launch and garnering 823 organic impressions. We utilise LinkedIn as it serves as the most crucial channel for engagement within project sectors. On LinkedIn, we aim to provide detailed information on achievements, events, publications, polls, and research results. Given that all partners and most of their collaborators have LinkedIn accounts, it is the optimal platform for disseminating information published on our website. Twitter, on the other hand, provides an easier way to track the market and observe the participation of other partners.

Figure 5. LinkedIn example post

3.4 Events

The ASSESS DHT consortium will present and discuss its work at events hosted by the project itself and at external events. These events will enable live discussion, whether online or face-to-face, to raise interest in the framework developed by the project and contribute substantially to the larger HTA discourse.

The main event format of interest to ASSESS DHT are conferences. ASSESS DHT consortium members have attended the following conferences since the beginning of the project:

- HTAi
- INAHTA
- ISPOR
- GetReal Conference
- Applied Economics in Digital Health
- Spanish Health Economics Conference

These events offer a unique opportunity for the consortium members to communicate on the project, whether it be in the context of panels, workshops, presentations or informal conversations. It is expected that contributions to and attendance at events will significantly increase as the project progresses.

The attendance at the following events is envisaged:

- HTAi (HTAi Annual Meeting)
- INAHTA
- ISPOR (International Society for Pharmacoeconomics and Outcomes Research, Annual ISPOR Europe Conference)
- EUHEA Biannual Conference and Seminar Series
- EPH Annual Conference (targeting their HTA section)
- EHMA Annual Conference
- European Observatory on Health Systems and Policies Webinars
- GIN Conference
- Mobile World Congress
- Digital Therapeutics Alliance Inaugural Summit
- European Society of Cardiology (ESC) Congress
- International Diabetes Federation (IDF) Congress
- Annual Conference of i-HD

Our partners' conferences will prominently feature ASSESS DHT results. In addition, empirica and i-HD will jointly organise the ASSESS DHT final conference as the dominant theme of the i-HD Annual Conference of 2026.

3.5 Dissemination materials

Dissemination materials, both physical and online, can help spread the ASSESS DHT's messaging to stakeholders through various formats. These formats are catered to the stakeholders the project wants to target, thus contributing to DO1, raising awareness, and DO2, engaging key stakeholders.

The project has already developed a visual identity (presented in D1.3 "Project handbook"), which is applied to all dissemination materials.

ASSESS DHT has developed a generic presentation on the project that can be utilised by all consortium partners and tailored to the specific interests of the stakeholders they are presenting to. Additionally, a two-pager has been developed to showcase the project aim and critical facts at a glance. These

materials allow the project partners to share information on the project and spark discussion on it in different settings. It is foreseen that further dissemination materials will be developed throughout the course of the project. For example, ASSESS DHT will develop explanatory materials on its outputs such as the framework for various stakeholders, such as decision makers, health professionals and the public.

Furthermore, the project may utilise specific dissemination material formats such as policy briefs led by TUB through their collaboration with the European Observatory on Health Systems and Policies to reach key stakeholders such as decision makers.

Development and harmonisation of methodologies for assessing digital health technologies in Europe

ASSESS DHT

About

ASSESS DHT is a European initiative that aims to increase the adoption of trustworthy and effective Digital Health Technologies (DHTs) across Europe, enabling a more coherent digital single market, for health systems and patients to access DHT from all over Europe and giving industry a European market.

Key aspects

CONSOLIDATION & PREPARATION	TOOLKIT DEVELOPMENT	TESTING & VALIDATION	UPTAKE & SUSTAINABILITY
DHT taxonomy & mapping	Tool: optimised evidence generation plans	Case study 1: Telehealth	Strategic partners & community building
Analysis of existing assessment approaches	Tool: validation for AI-based decision support systems	Case study 2: Digital Health Application	European repository: methods, results, evidence and sustainability
Frameworks & methods gap analysis	Guides: Interacting digital health tools	Case study 3: AI-based Digital Health Application	Public consultations
DHT data assessment criteria: Data-protection, interoperability, security, data quality, data bias, metadata handling	Life-cycle based assessment of digital health technologies	Case study 4: AI-based tech used in radiology (open call)	Expert groups (x4)
Compliance & compatibility: GDPR, AI ethics and regulation, cybersecurity, NIS, GDPR, EU AI Act	Overarching manual for assessment of DHT	Open call for further evidence submissions throughout EU and associated countries (x 5-10)	Sustainability roundtables (EU27 + Associated Countries)

Partners

The ASSESS-DHT consortium comprises 14 partners from 7 countries representing HTA, research organisations, DHT companies, professional and patient organisations as well as intergovernmental and multi-stakeholder associations at EU, Member State and regional level.

empirica | iHD The European Institute for Innovation through Health Data | Fundação Pública Andaluza Program y Social Compendio Salud Canaria | TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT DRESDEN | UNIVERSITÄT DUISBURG ESSEN | NICE National Institute for Health and Care Excellence | ainta | TLV | International Diabetes Federation | ULB UNIVERSITÉ LIBRE DE BRUXELLES | Tech4Care | bettercare

Contact

assess-dht.eu | @AssessDHT | Assess-DHT

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Figure 6. ASSESS DHT two-pager

3.6 (Scientific) publications

In order to contribute to the scientific discourse on HTA, ASSESS DHT will share insights generated throughout the course of the project in the format of publications. Further, scientific articles can help enhance ASSESS DHT's perceived legitimacy beyond the scientific community. Project results disseminated via scientific publications will primarily originate from the work of WP2 and WP3. Scientific publications, posters, and participation in conferences contribute to DO3 Scientific publications and conferences, thus promoting scientific work and ensuring that the projects' results are accepted by the scientific community.

Scientific publications by ASSESS DHT follow the guidelines for publication established in the consortium's publication policy, which was agreed upon by the PEC. ASSESS DHT is committed to publishing open access articles.

The project will further target journals such as:

- Value in Health – ISPOR Journal
- BMC Digital Health

- ScienceDirect - Health Technology
- European Journal of Public Health
- The Lancet Digital Health
- Frontiers in Artificial Intelligence
- Studies in Health Technology and Informatics
- International journal of technology assessment in health care
- European Heart Journal - Digital Health
- Frontiers in Digital Health
- PLOS Digital Health
- Journal of Medical Internet Research
- Health Policy
- SAGE Journals Digital Health
- Finnish Journal of eHealth and eWelfare

In addition, the European Commission “Open Research Europe” platform may be utilised and ResearchGate will be monitored. The following articles has already been published at the time of submission of this deliverable:

- Mathias, R., McCulloch, P., Chalkidou, A. *et al.* Digital health technologies need regulation and reimbursement that enable flexible interactions and groupings. *npj Digit. Med.* **7**, 148 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-024-01147-z>
- Mathias, R., McCulloch, P., Chalkidou, A. *et al.* How can regulation and reimbursement better accommodate flexible suites of digital health technologies?. *npj Digit. Med.* **7**, 170 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-024-01156-y>

4 Communication and dissemination tools and structures

This chapter presents an overview of the communication and dissemination tools and structures used by ASSESS DHT, namely

- The virtual communication office team
- Communication and dissemination reporting and planning tool
- Canva
- Webinar tools
- Collaboration platforms and tools for enabling interaction with stakeholders

4.1 Virtual Communication Office Team

The virtual Communication Office Team (vCOT) is comprised of members of each WP. People from all beneficiaries are invited to the vCOT to ensure full alignment with the project's messaging. The vCOT is led by empirica as the T1.6 lead. The vCOT takes place on a monthly basis in the format of an online Teams meeting. Additional meetings may be arranged depending on the needs of the work packages.

The vCOT is used to discuss the external communication of project activities and associated (social) media campaigns. In this context, the vCOT provides a dedicated platform for exploring ideas and proposals for media campaigns, gathering the consortium partner's input on them, and presenting media kits that partners may use to distribute ASSESS DHT content on their respective media channels.

4.2 Communication and dissemination reporting and planning tool

A communication and dissemination reporting tool was established in Excel to ensure a good overview of communication and dissemination activities across the consortium. The tool is available to all partners on the SharePoint utilised by the consortium. It contains information on events, publications, and other dissemination activities.

The events section includes a comprehensive list of all planned, ongoing, and realised events. Each entry is divided into the event name, date, location, target audience, and consortium partners involved. The aim of this section is to help track the consortium partners' participation in conferences, seminars, fairs, and other activities, ensuring that all events are well-documented and that further activities are followed up on.

The publication section aims to gather academic documents and publications produced by consortium partners. It is divided into title, authors, partners, link (if available), journal, and comments. This section is crucial for measuring the scientific output and research activities of each partner. Additionally, this document can be used to make announcements on project social media.

The dissemination section gathers information on other dissemination activities that do not fit in the events and publication sections. These activities can include press releases, blog entries, and more.

The tool is used during every vCOT meeting for collaborative stocktaking and to ensure that communication and dissemination activities are completed.

4.3 Canva

Canva³, a free-to-use online graphic design tool, is particularly well-suited for ASSESS DHT's social media materials. It offers a wide array of elements, icons, and graphics to choose from. Its user-friendly interface and comment feature make it effortless to create diverse visual formats, ranging from images to videos. Additionally, its ability to seamlessly transition between different frame sizes for various platforms, such as X and LinkedIn, facilitates the creation of consistent posts across different social media channels.

A brand kit was established on Canva to ensure that all visuals shared by ASSESS DHT follow a streamlined approach. This allows for the easy selection of the brand logo and colours and will contribute to the consistent visual identity of ASSESS DHT.

Figure 7. Examples of visual campaigns created using Canva

Figure 8. ASSESS DHT brand kit on Canva

³ <https://www.canva.com/>

4.4 Webinar tools

Webinars enable the ASSESS DHT consortium to communicate and discuss their project results and dedicated topics in an interactive yet moderated setting. They can further support the sustainability of communication by allowing for a recording of the session. Several consortium members have licenses to software that enables webinars. Microsoft Teams will be used as the default tool for webinars in ASSESS DHT. MS Teams Webinars⁴ enables the scheduling of webinars, registration of attendees, and analysis of attendees' data (in accordance with the GDPR).

4.5 Collaboration platforms and tools for enabling interaction with stakeholders

To enable online interactions within the consortium and with stakeholders, several tools may be used, two of which will be highlighted in the following. These tools may be used at consortium meetings and workshops, and conferences, but will be especially used at webinars to successfully gather feedback and enable collaboration during webinars.

Coordinator EMPIRICA has a license for the tool Mentimeter⁵. This tool enables live polls supporting several question types (e.g., multiple-choice and open-ended) to gather feedback in real-time. Participants can join the poll using a QR code or by accessing a URL on their device and entering a code-protected space without having to create an account. Feedback is thus anonymised (unless participants enter their names in open-ended questions).

FigJam⁶ is another tool that may be used by the project. Participants attending a FigJam session can access the webapp without having to create their own account. This tool can support collaborative activities through a flexible online environment. For example, it can be used for brainstorming sessions using through a sticky note feature, or for mapping ideas and processes using flowcharts. It will be particularly useful for supporting creative processes in internal meetings and can also be used for online workshops conducted by ASSESS DHT.

⁴ <https://www.microsoft.com/microsoft-teams/webinars>

⁵ <https://www.mentimeter.com/>

⁶ <https://www.figma.com/figjam/team-collaboration/>

5 Monitoring and reporting indicators and evaluation

This chapter presents an overview of the monitoring and reporting indicators and evaluation approach foreseen by ASSESS DHT. In order to obtain relevant statistics, the project employs specific tools to measure success, such as:

- Twitter⁷ and LinkedIn analytics
- Google analytics
- Google alerts
- Tracking system / excel updated via the WP lead and consortium members, offline and online, i.e. during the vCOT.

The table below lays out the specific impact indicators that ASSESS DHT will collect to measure the success of the project's communication and dissemination efforts.

Table 9. Impact indicators for ASSESS DHT communication targets

Nr	Indicator	Method of Measurement	Target
Website			
1	No. of unique visits to assess-dht.eu	Website statistics	10,000
2	No. of new events published assess-dht.eu	Website statistics	6
3	No. of news published on assess-dht.eu	Website statistics	30
4	No. of unique visitors to the ASSESS DHT repository	Website statistics	<500
Social media			
5	No. of social media campaigns	Project reporting, D1.6, D1.7	12
6	No. of tweets using the hashtag #assessdht	X statistics	50
7	No. of X accounts using the hashtag #assessdht	Hashtag tracking statistics	10
8	No. of followers of the project's X account	X statistics	200
9	No. of tweets by project account	X statistics	250
10	No. of followers of the project's LinkedIn page	LinkedIn statistics	800
11	No. of LinkedIn accounts using the hashtag #assessdht	Hashtag tracking statistics	100
12	No. of LinkedIn posts by project account	LinkedIn statistics	250
13	Post/tweet impression rate by the projects accounts	Project reporting, D1.6, D1.7	10%
Dissemination materials			
14	No. of explanatory dissemination materials included in the ASSESS DHT repository, addressing various groups (at least decision-makers, health professionals, public)	Project reporting, D1.7	3

⁷ X has recently changed its policy so that its analytics services are now only offered to premium subscribers. The consortium is currently considering whether these would provide an added benefit to its communication and dissemination efforts.

Nr	Indicator	Method of Measurement	Target
(Scientific) publications			
15	No. of academic and other scientific publications, open access white papers and position papers	Project reporting, D1.6, D1.7	6

The indicators will be monitored continuously throughout the project by the WP1 team and results reported in D1.6 and D1.7, namely Interim report on communication and dissemination [M18] and Final report on communication and dissemination impact [M36].

These deliverables will also provide additional information on the project's progress and success regarding its dissemination objectives, such as media (online and print) references to ASSESS DHT, and presentations at conferences. Furthermore, one of the project's specific communication targets that will be discussed in these documents is that the project website, social media accounts, events and targeted stakeholder communications regarding the assessment framework, pathways, tools and online repository should reach over >500 persons covering all target stakeholder groups. To this end, project will supplement the information it has on the visitors of the repository on the ASSESS DHT website with its visitor demographics on social media (i.e., LinkedIn analytics provide information on the page visitor's job function) and information on the broad stakeholder groups as laid out in chapter 2 from their own events (in person and online) in accordance with the GDPR. This supplementary information will serve as a proxy to check whether all stakeholder groups are likely to have been reached with the repository on the website as collecting this information from website visitors is not feasible due to GDPR constraints.

In addition to the reporting in these documents, a separate process for reporting on the project milestones will be established. The envisaged communication campaigns regarding the nine project milestones lay at the heart of ASSESS DHT's communication strategy as highlighted throughout this document. In order to evaluate the success of these vital campaigns and to learn for future campaigns, the project will create a report including statistics to communicate to the European Commission.